

INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON GLOBAL
& EMERGING TRENDS

ICGET

**VISIONS OF THE FUTURE: INNOVATIONS,
TECHNOLOGIES & APPLICATIONS**

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ABOUT THE ICGET SERIES

The International Conference on Global & Emerging Trends (ICGET) series is a forum for showcasing leading visionary, multidisciplinary research, developments, and technologies. It provides a platform for presenting the latest work, products, and systems related to global changes in the human society and technological advancements. The ICGET series focuses on the following key areas:

- Promoting industry-academia & interdisciplinary collaborations.
- Encouraging laboratory-to-market transitions of research outputs.
- Supporting budding researchers for mentorship and publications.
- Creating a platform to nurture & promote research dissemination .

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barriers combine to widen adaptation and adoption gap. In much the same way, issues typical of pronunciation, intonation and accent difficulties are vital variables that explain the root cause of anxiety. To assess and ensure the vision of a multilingual tomorrow in addressing language anxiety through educational technology, mixed- methods approach was employed, combining qualitative interviews and surveys to gather insights from students, educators, and language experts. Key factors contributing to language anxiety were identified. Effectiveness of educational technology interventions in reducing such anxiety and promoting multilingualism were evaluated. The study provided practical recommendations for tomorrow's policymakers, educators, and education technology developers to design and consider integration windows where culture and conversation partner deficiencies can be remedied; through educational events like debates, quizzes and symposia improvements can be attained while commercial advertisements are tailored towards seeking for adoption of second language in commerce and major cultural activities.

[3026] Public School Leaders' Perceptions of School Readiness for Data-Driven Leadership in the United Arab Emirates : A Mixed-Methods Study.

Mahmoud Hamash (Universiti Teknologi Malaysia), Hanan Ghreir (Liverpool John Moores University) and Hasnah Mohamed (Universiti Teknologi Malaysia).

There is a growing need for Data-Driven Leadership (DDL) in UAE. While the implementation frameworks serve as a ground approach for implementing DDL, there has yet to be an application of this concept in the UAE school context. This

research aims to assess the readiness of Western region cycle two and Three public schools for DDL implementation. The study used the exploratory sequential mixed methodology design based on the Active Implementation Framework (AIF) drivers. In the first qualitative research phase, the researcher used the Scoping review procedure to scope sixty-three literature sources, and in the second quantitative research phase, the researcher surveyed the research sample of sixteen school principals from nineteen cycle two and three public schools in the Western region, using the School Principal questionnaire, the sampling method used was simple random sampling. And then descriptive analysis was used to analyse the collected data. The research findings suggest that principals are more ready for DDL in terms of organisational drivers than competency drivers. However, the level of readiness of the leadership for DDL remains somewhat uncertain, with items for that driver falling between the highest and middle-scoring groups. School principals identified competency, organizational, and technical leadership drivers as key implementation drivers for improving DDL in their schools. The research recommends further research to understand the role of adaptive leadership in successful DDL implementation. In conclusion, this research has provided valuable insight into the implementation of DDL in Western region cycle two and three public schools. and highlighted the importance of various AIF drivers to the successful implementation of DDL.